

A Smart Material Flapping Wing Micro Rotorcraft

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Summary

In this project, investigation was made into the design, analysis and experiment of a smart material flapping wing devices for micro air vehicles (MAV). Attention was mainly focused on the design of a simple, reliable and lightweight flapping mechanism to achieve two most challenging objectives. Firstly enlarge the piezoelectric actuator motion for adequate flapping amplitude for forward flight; secondly achieve hovering or very low speed flight. Apart from the traditional rigid lever mechanism and symmetrical flapping wing configuration, this current research produced a couple of new design concepts including a compliant joint and a flapping rotor MAV configuration. Structural resonance and aeroelastic beneficial effect have been considered in the system design to reduce power demand and enhance aerodynamic performance.

Example and Results

The work covers design, modelling, analysis, manufacture and experiment of the mechanism as illustrated in Fig.1 and a prototype MAV as shown in Fig.2. The actuator used in the study is a pre-stressed TH-7R and TH-8R type Thunders made of multi-layer composite being cut into strips. The bar and wing were made from carbon/epoxy composite and the compliant joint is made of nylon flexures. A set of compliant joint mechanism made of two-bar up to four-bar has been made to amplify a small actuator motion to a large flapping angle. Test results for different flexural thickness and lengths were obtained to study the effect on amplitude and frequency of the flapping wings. The power supply units used include ISO-TECH ISP60IA and 603D, function generator GFG-8216A and in-house built OP Amp-90 amplifier. A peak-to-peak voltage of 300V DC (around -110 to +180V) was applied to the actuators.

Two different weight of flapping wings with a 3-layer 7 mm compliant joint were made for the experiment. Test was carried out for the wing with and without a skin cover. This allows a separation of the total force from the aerodynamic or inertia force measured at the wing root. Some of measurement results are listed in Table 1 below.

Figure 1. A compliant joint mechanism

Figure 2. A micro flapping wing rotorcraft

Table 1. Results of the system with 3-layer 7mm compliant joint

	Wing 1 - 295.7 V (-116.8 to 178.9)	Wing 2 - 295.7 V
weight without skin (gm)	0.558	0.220
wing tip displacement (mm)	2.5	-
flapping frequency (Hz)	6.8	9.1
flapping angle (deg)	28	22
weight with skin cover (gm)	0.682	0.334
flapping frequency (Hz)	5.0	5.5
flapping angle (deg)	11.0	9.0

Conclusions

The results have shown that the compliant joint amplification mechanism is simple and effective. The flapping wing rotation angle can reach up to 50 deg in the traditional mechanism and the frequency up to 9 Hz. For the complaint joint mechanism, the flapping wing can rotate up to 28 deg at 6.8 Hz and produce a powerful aerodynamic force. The test result of a 9 gm micro flapping wing rotorcraft prototype shows that the innovative design concept for hovering and very low speed flight is feasible.

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